

EDUCATION OF GIRLS AND WOMEN – OPPORTUNITIES AND OBSTACLES*Ms . Shilpa and Neetyanandi**Student Teacher MES's Pillai College of Education and Research , Chembur***Abstract***“Education is the only key to empower girls and Focus on girl education and develop the nation”**-- Srajansethiya*

According to the Constitution of India, education is a fundamental right of every child. However, the situation in India is dreadful because girls in many parts are not given the option of attending school. How can education be denied based on gender? By denying education to a girl child, we are putting humanity to shame. Our indian constitution say's Girls' education is a strategic development priority. Better educated women tend to be healthier, participate more in the formal labor market, earn higher incomes, have fewer children, marry at a later age, and enable better health care and education for their children, should they choose to become mothers. Women and girls in the developing world are often denied opportunities for education. World Education believes that education for girls and women is the single most effective way to improve the lives of individual families as well as to bring economic development to poor communities worldwide. When the Girl Child Education , They go to school, help with housework, work in factories, make friends, care for elder and younger family members and prepare themselves to take on the responsibilities of adulthood. Girls play multiple roles in the household, society and the economy. Economic independence and empowerment will come when we educate the girl child. Improved life: Educating of the girl child helps in the improvement of a good life. ... Improved health: Educated girls bring an awareness of the important of hygiene and health. Through education, they can lead a healthy life style.

Education Lays the Foundation

Imparting education sustains human values and triggers learning along with critical thinking. Girl child education is the key weapon towards development and empowerment of women who face suppression from the patriarchal society. Educating a girl child makes her aware and bold. She will stand up and fight for her rights. The importance of education for girl child will be seen when she will raise her voice against societal evils inflicted upon women like dowry, female foeticide, sexual harassment, child marriage, etc.

Girl Child Education Schemes by the Government

Indian Government, both at the Central and State level have taken conscious efforts to promote education for the girl child. All girl children are entitled to free education till Class 8 under the Right to Education Act. To address the declining sex ratio and to raise awareness regarding the importance of girl education, Prime Minister Narendra Modi launched the Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao scheme. Several State Governments provide free education for the girl child, free textbooks, educational loan, Sukanya Samridhi Yojna and many other policies to help girl child obtain a formal education .

Methodology

The data was collected from 60 student teacher through a survey. The data was analyzed qualitatively using coding method. This was a part of the ki and ka project .

Conclusion :

Women, the first teachers of the child, who help them for education and build the child future. So, definitely the education of women is realized to be the most essential part for the development of the society. The first Prime Minister of India Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru strongly stressed on women education. According to him “Education of a boy is education of one person, but education of a girl is the education of the entire family.” The duty of a mother doesn’t finish with giving birth to a number of children but also it's the duty of mother is to teach the child how to survive in the society and Hence our human community also should realize the need of their education for

the betterment of the society as a whole. Women education can help in solving their problems also like birth control, menace of drugs, poverty, dowry system, bride burning cases, inequality of women in the society and child labor etc.